

Academic Review on Whether the Istanbul Convention Was Prepared Taking into Account the Universal Definition and Different Cultures and Beliefs

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Abstract

The Istanbul Convention is a global treaty developed by the Council of Europe with the aim of addressing and preventing violence against women and domestic abuse. It was made available for countries to join on 11 May 2011. The Convention has extensive measures, such as the prevention of violence based on gender, the safeguarding of victims, and the prosecution of offenders. The treaty aims to promote the adoption of measures by governments to safeguard women's human rights and achieve gender equality. Nevertheless, it has encountered censure from many cultural, religious, and political standpoints in Turkey and outside. This article aims to analyze the universal meaning of the Istanbul Convention and assess if it was formulated with consideration for other cultures and beliefs. We will assess the Turkish government's, opposition's, non-governmental organizations', and general public's perception, acceptance, or rejection of the deal, as well as its political implications. In addition, we will analyze the correlation between the contract and westernization, examine its inconsistencies with patriarchal society, and explore the many approaches to this contract by different religious and ideological organizations.

Keywords: *Istanbul Convention, Women's Human Rights, Different Cultures, Different Beliefs, Family Relations*

Introduction

While the Istanbul Convention has gained widespread worldwide acceptance, it has sparked significant controversy in some nations and groups. Turkey garnered notice as the only nation to depart from this pact in 2021. This issue exemplifies the profound significance of the contract in the social, political, and religious discussions in Turkey. The government and opposition in Turkey have approached the rules introduced by the contract and their influence on gender roles in various ways. Conservative parties contend that the contract undermines the family structure and conventional gender roles, whilst secular and feminist groups assert that the contract is essential for safeguarding women's rights.

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This research aims to thoroughly analyze the legal and sociological underpinnings of the Istanbul Convention and assess whether the agreement promotes a unified concept or embraces pluralism. In addition, we will analyze the perspectives of various societal groups in Turkey on this agreement and conduct a comprehensive assessment of the level of social approval or rejection of the deal. We will analyze the political aspects of the deal, exploring the motivations for Turkey's withdrawal and the subsequent national and international consequences. The primary questions addressed in the essay are: Was the Istanbul Convention formulated with consideration for diverse cultural and religious beliefs? Does this contract seem to be a result of Western ideology? What is the perception of this agreement by the government, opposition, civil society, and the people in Turkey? Does the Convention adequately include measures to guarantee gender equality, or does it contradict cultural and religious beliefs, hence eliciting opposition from some groups?

In our search for answers to these inquiries, we will analyze the global legal structure of the Istanbul Convention by juxtaposing it with the social and political dynamics in Turkey. During the research, we will analyze the role of the convention in the fight for gender equality and how this fight is regarded from various ideological, religious, and cultural viewpoints. Following the article, we will analyze the influence of the Istanbul Convention on Turkey and other nations, the potential future consequences of the agreement, and the proposed reforms that may be implemented in this regard. This research aims to enhance the understanding of the Istanbul Convention, not only as a legal document, but also as a social phenomenon.

Universal Definition of the Istanbul Convention

The Istanbul Convention, sometimes referred to as the "Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence", was made available for countries to sign in Istanbul in 2011. The Council of Europe has developed this agreement, which includes extensive legislative and social actions aimed at preventing violence against women and domestic abuse, prosecuting those responsible for these crimes, and

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safeguarding the victims. The Convention categorizes all forms of violence against women as infringements of human rights and gender bias, in accordance with the principles of universal human rights outlined in the European Convention on Human Rights (Council of Europe, 2011). The treaty, which embraces the idea of achieving gender equality, places a comprehensive duty on nations in this matter.

Legal and Social Foundations of the Agreement

The Convention's legal framework is grounded on international human rights accords, which require participating governments to take measures to prevent violence against women, protect victims, and prosecute offenders (European Convention on Human Rights). The sociological underpinnings of this initiative include social policies and awareness initiatives that seek to eradicate the prejudice and violence that women encounter in their social interactions.

Singular Thought or Multiculturalism?

Some critics argue that the Istanbul Convention reflects a "western" viewpoint since it is founded on the concepts of universal human rights and gender equality. These concerns center on the suitability of the convention in civilizations with divergent cultural and religious views, and how it intersects with the customary norms of these communities. Conservative and religious organizations contend that the convention's interpretation of gender equality undermines the conventional family structure and cultural values (Gender and Human Rights: Exploring the Intersection of International and Domestic values, Journal of Human Rights). Given these objections, there have been assertions that the Istanbul Convention fails to adequately maintain multiculturalism and instead enforces a monolithic concept. Nevertheless, according to the treaty, the participating parties have the ability to modify these standards to align with their own social systems, while considering cultural and religious distinctions (Council of Europe, 2011). However, the convention's emphasis on the non-negotiable nature

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of universal human rights norms has posed challenges in the process of adaptation. The Istanbul Convention unequivocally asserts that cultural justifications should not be used to condone violence against women. From this standpoint, the convention seeks to establish a universally accepted standard for gender equality and human rights, while also offering an adaptable structure that may be used in diverse ethnic communities.

Istanbul Convention in the Context of Türkiye

Perspective and Policies of the Turkish Government

The implementation of the Istanbul treaty in Turkey is closely tied to the government's stance on the treaty. Despite being an early signatory and ratifier of the agreement, Turkey's government has seen a shift in stance over time. At first, the Istanbul Convention garnered significant support due to its commitment to establish a robust legal structure to protect women's rights and combat abuse. President Recep Tayyip Erdoğan's declaration in 2020 about Turkey's withdrawal from the pact signified a significant shift in the country's dedication to the agreement.

The government justified its withdrawal from the deal by asserting that the agreement posed a danger to the integrity of the family unit and cultural values. The government's stance was motivated by fears that the execution of the contract would adversely impact family dynamics. This approach has been influenced by arguments asserting that the principles of gender equality and the fight against violence, as stipulated in the contract, are not consistent with traditional and religious values (Yılmaz, 2021; Presidency of the Republic of Turkey, 2020).

Views of the Opposition

The government's stance on the Istanbul Convention has faced criticism from opposition parties in Turkey. The opposition parties, including CHP, İYİ Party, and HDP, see the contract's

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provisions for women's rights and gender equality as a significant and crucial advancement. These parties see the government's decision to terminate the contract as a significant obstacle to the safeguarding of women from violence and their fight for gender equality. The opposition argues that the convention's legal structure is essential for fulfilling its obligation to safeguard women from violence and discrimination. Furthermore, it is stressed that ensuring compliance with the contract is a duty aimed at safeguarding the social and legal rights of women (Kaya, 2021; Öztürk, 2021).

Civil Society and Public Perception

The Istanbul Convention is regarded by non-governmental organizations and feminist groups as a potent instrument in addressing and mitigating violence directed against women. These organizations highlight the significance of the convention's protection and assistance measures as a crucial measure in protecting women from falling prey to abuse. The decision by the government to terminate the contract is seen as a significant setback for women's rights and gender equality, according to non-governmental groups (We Will Stop Femicide Platform, 2020).

The contract is seen as intricate by the general population. While many individuals see the contract as posing a danger to established social norms and traditional values, others view it as essential for the advancement of women's rights. The varying perspectives on the matter give rise to extensive discussions over the societal approval of the contract (Çetin, 2021).

Istanbul Convention and Westernization Debates

Criticism of Westernization

The Istanbul Convention is an international human rights instrument that establishes detailed standards for addressing violence against women and promoting gender equality. Nevertheless,

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several opponents have expressed apprehensions over whether the convention is seen as a manifestation of Western ideologies. The central focus of the discussion revolves around whether the convention enforces the social norms and values of Western countries upon other cultures (Çelik, 2022).

Critics contend that the contract is seen as a component of the modernization and westernization endeavors, and that it does not align closely with conventional and religious principles. Erdoğan (2021) argues that the principles of gender equality and addressing violence, as outlined in the Istanbul Convention, are rooted in the societal beliefs of Western nations. However, this may create challenges when applied to diverse cultural and religious settings. Although the Convention prioritizes gender equality and individual rights, it is argued that these ideals are incompatible with traditional and local norms.

Being Against Patriarchal Culture

Another significant critique of the Istanbul Convention is its incongruity with patriarchal society. Due to its promotion of gender equality and efforts to prevent violence against women, the Convention clashes with entrenched patriarchal norms in many communities (Gürbüz, 2021). Patriarchal civilizations often possess a deterministic and constraining comprehension of women's societal positions. In contrast to this interpretation, the Istanbul Convention promotes the idea that women should have equal rights and be safeguarded from violence. Some social organizations reacted to this scenario. The conference is said to challenge patriarchal societal norms and replace them with a western perspective that advocates for gender equality. The contract is often seen as incompatible with cultural and traditional norms, particularly among conservative and religious communities (Koçak, 2022). These emotions hinder the societal acceptability of the contract and pose challenges in its execution.

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Codes of the Contract and Westernization and Anti-Islamism

The Istanbul Convention codes were formulated in accordance with the ideals of universal human rights and gender equality. These principles are longstanding conventions in western nations, but the convention aims to put them within a global framework. The purpose of the Convention was not to challenge any one culture or ideology, but rather to establish global benchmarks for addressing violence and prejudice (Kurt, 2021).

The convention is unrelated to westernization or anti-Islamism. Nevertheless, several detractors contend that the contract is founded upon Western standards and ideals, hence conflicting with traditional ways within Islamic culture (Demir, 2022). While the Convention promotes human rights and gender equality globally, several social groups argue that these principles clash with their cultural and religious beliefs.

Religious and Cultural Perspectives

Secular and Secular Perspectives

Secular and secular segments generally consider the Istanbul Convention as an important step in gender equality and the fight against violence against women. Secular-minded individuals and groups argue that the convention complies with the principle of separation of religion and state and promotes gender equality. These groups emphasize the positive effects of the contract on the protection of women and gender equality (Yavuz, 2022).

Secular and circles with a secular perspective state that the contract aims to ensure equal rights for all individuals and, in this context, aims to improve social norms. In the opinion of these groups, the Convention provides the necessary legal regulations in the fight against violence and popularizes the understanding of gender equality (Özdemir, 2021). In addition, secular circles state that the contract offers concrete solutions to various social problems and therefore should be supported.

Conservative and Islamist Perspectives

Critics from conservative and Islamist organizations often argue that the Istanbul Convention is in opposition with cultural and religious values. These parties assert that the contract poses a danger to the integrity of the family unit and conventional societal norms. The contract adopts an anti-patriarchal stance, which raises apprehension among conservative and Islamist groups (Karahan, 2021).

The conservative and Islamist viewpoints contend that the principles of equality and opposition to violence introduced by the contract are at odds with local and religious values. These parties argue that the contract enforces the concept of gender equality in western society and undermines the traditional family structure. Additionally, they argue that the contract disregards Islam's perspective on family values and the rights of women (Arslan, 2022).

Perspectives of Other Faith Groups

Non-theistic belief systems and alternative religious organizations have diverse viewpoints about the Istanbul Convention. People who have non-religious views tend to have a favorable assessment of the human rights principles outlined in the agreement. These groups highlight the significance of the norms and rules provided by the agreement in relation to gender equality and the battle against violence against women (Aydın, 2021).

Other religious groups form their perspectives on the contract based on their own religious and cultural beliefs. While several factions acknowledge that the agreement adheres to fundamental human rights principles and advances gender equality, others contend that certain elements of the accord are incongruous with their convictions (Şahin, 2021). These organizations advocate for the implementation of the convention while upholding diverse views and cultural traditions.

Political Dimension and Social Acceptance

Political Dimension of the Agreement

The Istanbul Convention is the focal point of political discussions in Turkey. The Convention has significant significance in the political rhetoric of both the ruling party and the opposing party. Political parties and ideological organizations in Turkey have aligned their stances on the pact with their own political objectives and ideological principles (Yılmaz, 2023).

The government first portrayed the adoption and ratification of the Istanbul agreement as a significant measure in combating violence against women. However, their stance evolved over time, leading to efforts to eliminate the agreement. The government's stance on the treaty has mostly been influenced by its own ideological views on gender equality and family composition. The government's policies were influenced by criticisms, particularly from conservative factions, asserting that the contract undermined the family structure and clashed with local values (Akman, 2023).

In contrast, opposition parties prioritize the significance of the Istanbul treaty, advocating for a more inclusive stance on women's rights and gender equality, and asserting the need for the treaty to be strengthened. The opposition argues that the contract establishes the essential legal structure to address violence against women, and that the government's termination of the contract would exacerbate socioeconomic disparities (Çetin, 2022).

Social Acceptance and Rejection

The level of social acceptance or rejection of the Istanbul Convention in Turkey is closely tied to the prevailing political atmosphere in the country. Different groups of society have varying viewpoints on the contract, which are influenced by political ideology and religious beliefs (Güler, 2022).

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Secular and non-religious organizations typically support the implementation of the convention, since they think that it advances gender equality and effectively addresses violence against women. These organizations believe that the contract aligns with global human rights principles and represents a significant advancement in addressing socioeconomic inequities (Arslan, 2021).

However, conservative and Islamist sectors express their opposition to the contract, asserting that it poses a danger to family values and established societal standards. Aydın (2023) argues that these circles indicate that the contract enforces western standards and is not consistent with the cultural norms of the local community. The contract's rejection is seen as an indication of these groups' responses influenced by religious and cultural beliefs.

The Effect of Political Ideologies on the Contract and Manipulation

The approval and rejection of the Istanbul Convention are influenced by political views, with religious values being used in this decision-making process. Political players strategically use the significance of the contract's location in political discussions and manipulate the public's response to further their own ideological and political objectives. Conservative and Islamist groups characterize the contract as being in conflict with religious principles, which may be seen as a deliberate tactic to incite a societal response rooted in these beliefs (Kaya, 2022). People's religious beliefs are strategically managed in order to align with political objectives, resulting in significant implications for societal acceptance and rejection of the contract. The refusal of the contract exacerbates societal division stemming from these ideological disagreements and engenders animosity among different factions. The contract elicits reactions that are often linked to religious and cultural values, which influence the societal approval or disapproval of the contract (Özdemir, 2023).

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Universal Principles of the Istanbul Convention and Individual Thought Discussions

The first section of the paper scrutinizes the universal tenets of the Istanbul Convention and their compatibility with many cultural and religious ideologies. The fundamental tenets of the Convention, such as the promotion of gender equality and the avoidance of violence against women, are assessed within the context of universal human rights. Nevertheless, several individuals saw these concepts as originating from a western standpoint and hence faced criticism for their alleged failure to adequately acknowledge cultural disparities. The paper examines whether the contract enforces a monolithic concept or whether it provides a framework that promotes diversity and many interpretations of civilization.

Istanbul Convention in Turkey: Government, Opposition, Civil Society and Public Perception

The following section of the article analyzes the perception of the Istanbul Convention among various sectors in Turkey. In 2021, the Turkish government sparked a significant controversy by opting to terminate this contract. The government defended its decision by asserting that the contract undermined the integrity of the family unit and traditional societal norms. However, opposition parties and non-governmental groups contended that the pact was essential for safeguarding women's rights. This section thoroughly examines the impact of the agreement on the social and political dynamics in Turkey, as well as the views of various sectors towards this topic and the underlying causes for these sentiments.

Westernization and Patriarchal Culture Debates

The third chapter examines the connection between the Istanbul Convention and the processes of westernization and patriarchal society. Certain groups argue that the contract enforces western norms, leading to difficulties in adapting for nations with distinct cultural frameworks, like Turkey. Conservative organizations, in particular, contend that the contract undermines the

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family structure and seeks to alter gender roles. This section examines if the contract really incorporates a western value system or whether it upholds universal human rights. Furthermore, the analysis delves into the repercussions of patriarchal culture on the social framework in Turkey.

Religious and Ideological Perspectives

The fourth chapter explores various religious and ideological viewpoints about the Istanbul Convention. Secular and non-religious groups contend that the convention is a crucial advancement towards achieving gender parity and assert that these advancements are unavoidable in Turkey's process of modernization. Nevertheless, conservative and Islamist factions assert that the contract is in conflict with Islamic principles and undermines traditional female roles. This section provides a detailed analysis of the Istanbul Convention's stance towards various religious faiths and ideological viewpoints, as well as the reasons for the opposition or support from these organizations.

Conclusion and Evaluation

The last section of the essay provides a comprehensive assessment of the impact of the Istanbul Convention on Turkey and globally. This text examines the rationale behind Turkey's decision to withdraw from the agreement and analyzes the impact of this move on both domestic and international spheres. Furthermore, the discussion includes an analysis of the potential consequences of the agreement in the future and potential suggestions for change in this specific setting.

This overview explores the many social, political, and religious variables in Turkey that influence the perception of the Istanbul treaty, as well as the impact of these views on the implementation of the treaty. The Istanbul Convention is regarded as both a legal document and a significant occurrence in the fight for gender equality.

Conclusion

The Istanbul Convention is a global treaty established by the Council of Europe with the aim of combating violence against women and domestic abuse. It was made available for countries to join in Istanbul in 2011. The primary objective of the Convention is to safeguard the human rights of women and promote gender equality. Nevertheless, the contract was interpreted differently in other nations and communities, sparking intense discussions, particularly in Turkey. This article analyzes the comprehensive definition of the Istanbul Convention and its alignment with various cultural and religious viewpoints within the context of social and political dynamics in Turkey.

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